

Deciphering Cyber-Security Certifications: An Ontological Journey through Composite Systems and their certification

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Abstract - As cyber-physical systems become increasingly interconnected and complex, ensuring their cyber security becomes paramount. Composite systems, comprised of multiple interconnected components, present unique challenges for cyber security certification due to their dynamic nature and diverse elements and used technologies. This paper will propose the development of an ontology specifically tailored for the cyber security certification of composite systems. Ontologies provide a structured framework for representing knowledge, allowing for semantic interoperability and in future automated reasoning. This ontology also aims to capture the intricate relationships between components, vulnerabilities, threats, and security controls within composite systems. Multi-layered approach employed, encompassing both technical and organizational aspects of cyber security, comprehensively address certification requirements. Also, we discuss the practical implications of proposed ontology in streamlining certification procedures, enhancing risk management, and promoting trustworthiness in composite systems. Through this work, we strive to contribute to the advancement of cyber security certification practices, EU regulation in the context of evolving composite systems (EU Common Criteria Framework).

Keywords—Cybersecurity certification, semantic ontology, knowledge representation, composite systems, formalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, authors embark on a comprehensive exploration of the complex landscape of cyber-security certifications. With an ever-expanding array of interconnected systems and technologies, understanding the certification process is paramount for ensuring robust digital defences. Through an ontological lens, authors will try to delve into the complexities of composite systems, analysing their structural composition, operational dynamics, and inherent vulnerabilities.

The research aims to illuminate the nuanced interplay between evolving security standards and the dynamic cyber threat landscape, shedding light on the challenges and opportunities inherent in certifying complex digital ecosystems. By unravelling the intricacies of certification within this context, this research will offer valuable insights for practitioners, policymakers, and stakeholders alike, facilitating informed decision-making and enhancing the resilience of modern digital infrastructures.

In today's interconnected digital landscape, the significance of cyber-security certification for *products, processes, and services* cannot be overstated. Such certification ensures that technological entities adhere to stringent standards, mitigating the risks of cyber threats and safeguarding sensitive data. By validating the robustness of cyber defences, certification fosters trust among consumers, enhances organizational resilience, and promotes innovation in an increasingly digitized world.

Certification serves as a form of assurance for consumers, businesses, and stakeholders. It demonstrates that a product, process, or service has undergone rigorous testing and meets predefined security criteria, thereby offering confidence in its reliability and trustworthiness.

Moreover, certification plays a pivotal role in regulatory compliance. Many industries and jurisdictions mandate specific cyber-security standards and certifications to ensure the protection of sensitive information and compliance with legal requirements. Adhering to these standards not only helps organizations avoid potential legal repercussions but also strengthens their resilience against cyber threats.

Composite systems, comprised of diverse hardware, software, and networks, pose unique challenges in ensuring holistic cyber resilience. From managing interoperability issues to addressing potential points of compromise across integrated systems, certifying composite systems demands comprehensive strategies that encompass diverse technologies and threat landscapes. Embracing this complexity is crucial for effectively safeguarding critical infrastructure, sensitive data, and ensuring the trustworthiness of interconnected systems in today's digital ecosystem.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CURRENT REQUIREMENTS

NIST in their terms define certification as “a comprehensive assessment of the management, operational, and technical security controls in an information system, in support of security accreditation, to determine whether the controls are implemented correctly, operating as intended, and producing the expected outcome to meet the security requirements for the system” [1].

Every cybersecurity certification process requires the formal, independent evaluation which need to be done by an accredited body against defined set of criteria or standards. The certificate indicating conformance will be issued. A comprehensive set of rules, technical requirements and standards, procedures are defined in cybersecurity certification scheme proposed by EUCSA (EU Cyber Security Act) and those may apply to the certification of specific products, services or processes [2].

At the time of writing this paper EUCC was adopted [3], and EUCS, EU5G and EUAI are under development [4]. Some countries have also some national schemes (i.e. BSI in Germany, NSCIB in Netherland [5], etc.), as well as some world-wide accepted schemes (NIST [6], [7], NESAS [8], etc.)

In the content of necessity of cybersecurity certification few EU regulation need to be emphasis: CSA (Cyber Security Act) [9], regulation which among other sets the framework for establishing of EU cybersecurity certification scheme. This scheme should ensure “adequate level” of cyber-security for any ICT products, services or processes.

From another side, CRA (Cyber Resilience Act) [10], regulate a cyber-security requirement for “products with digital elements”. This regulative which is now in the process to be adopted, will bring more trust to the digital products and increase the level of security if any product which will be available on the EU market.

The simple question arises here: why certification of composite system is so special? IT products in common way are not simple, they frequently consist of multiple components (composite IT products), with only some undergoing evaluation. It's common for individual product components to be assessed independently, leading to the challenge of integrating the security assurances of these separate elements to establish the overall security assurance of the product.

A composite product consists of at least two different parts, whereby one of them represents a single product having already been evaluated/certified. The composite ToE comprises the whole composite product, i.e. the certified product is declared to be part of the composite ToE [11], [12]. So, with the challenge of composite system certification also faced ECSO in the published research document, ensuring the security of such systems requires evaluating not just individual elements, but also their interactions and dependencies [13]. Additionally, diverse technologies and standards used in composite systems further complicate the certification process, necessitating comprehensive and adaptable assessment frameworks to mitigate potential vulnerabilities effectively [14].

III. METHODOLOGY AND ONTOLOGY DESIGN

The methodology utilized in the research employs an ontological approach as its central framework. Beginning with the construction of a comprehensive ontology, key concepts and relationships within cyber-security certifications are systematically defined and structured. Through rigorous ontological analysis, the intricate interconnections between composite systems and their certification processes are elucidated.

This method allows for a deep exploration of the underlying semantics and semantics of cyber-security certification, facilitating a nuanced understanding that transcends surface-level observations.

Ontology as a “explicit specification of the conceptualization process” exists for a decade [15], and in IT field is commonly used for knowledge organization and classification and mostly finished in the taxonomy phase. The idea in this paper was to use this methodology to create taxonomy and after that formalize the concepts which are most relevant for the topic. Created ontology will be publicly available in the repository [29].

There is a huge number of published papers which consider ontology methodology in context of cybersecurity, but not in cybersecurity certification domain. In their research, the authors dealt with the problem of cyber-forensic ontology [16], digital evidence ontology [17], GDPR [18], IS [19], as well as dynamic analysis of the IT systems [20].

Cyber-security certification, especially if we consider composite systems, is very complex domain and there are a lot of concepts which should be organized and indexed in the proper way. This organization will give us a common vocabulary and classification and help to better understand the domain. Such taxonomy can be used as a starting point for creating the ontology and formal description of the knowledge in cyber-security certification domain. Common ontology representation languages comprise OWL/RDF and SWRL [21], [22], [23].

There are a few ENISAs proposed taxonomies in cyber security domain which could be here (re)used:

- Incident classification taxonomy [24],
- Threat taxonomy [25],
- Resilience taxonomy [26],
- Supply-chain attacks taxonomy [27].

Our proposed taxonomy for cyber-security certification was build using Bottom-up (Deductive) methods on the way that all terms relevant for the domain are collected and reviewed by the experts and classified in the right groups.

The main groups are defined as follows:

- Stakeholders,
- Certification Scheme,
- Standards,
- Tools,
- Certification Scope,
- Protection Profile,
- Assurance Level,
- Certification Criteria,
- Result of the Certification,
- Security Target.

The basic taxonomy, which will be used as a starting point for ontology definition, is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Basic taxonomy defined for this purpose

Next step in the process of modelling the knowledge in the domain, is the systematic description of the terms, definition of the attributes and characteristics and finally formalize the proposed concept and taxonomy. This was done using Ontology modelling and Protégé platform/tool [28].

The aim of making such an ontology is to precisely define the cyber-security certification domain and fill the gaps in already proposed ontologies with the aim that this formal described knowledge can be used not only by the expert (people), but also to be understandable and readable for the machine.

The proposed, holistic ontology is presented in Figure 2, and could be downloaded from the repository [29].

Fig. 2. Proposed ontology

The main classes are proposed in the taxonomy and for those are defined attributes (properties), as well as relationship with other(s). Some individuals are also created which will be used for testing purpose. With the formal description in Protégé platform, ontology will be enriched in the future, because ontology is not fixed and behave like living tissue.

Some formalizations of the knowledge which are incorporate in first version are:

- NAB accredit CAB,
- CAB perform CA (Low, Intermediate, and High AL) of the ToE,
- Vendor/Manufacturer/Service provider can perform CA (Low AL),
- Vendor/Manufacturer/Service need some certification services,
- CAB can certify ToE,
- SDOs develop standards,
- ToE evaluated against PP,
- ToE meets specific requirements standard,
- Every ToE must have AL,

- Certification have some status,
- CAB use some tools.

Considering composite systems, understanding the relationships and interactions between components is crucial. Simply assessing each component individually isn't sufficient because vulnerabilities can arise from how these components interact and communicate with each other.

Comprehensive certification requires evaluating the system, considering how its interconnected parts might introduce security risks.

Let's represent simple use-case using OWL [21].

```
# Classes
ex:CompositeSystem rdf:type owl:Class .
ex:Product rdf:type owl:Class .
ex:CommonCriteriaCertification rdf:type owl:Class .
ex:ProtectionProfile rdf:type owl:Class .

# Properties
ex:hasComponent rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty .
ex:achievesCertification rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty .
ex:meetsProtectionProfile rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty .

# Individuals
ex:SomeCompositeSystem rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ;
    rdf:type ex:CompositeSystem .

ex:SomeProduct rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ;
    rdf:type ex:Product ;
    ex:achievesCertification ex:CCCertification ;
    ex:meetsProtectionProfile ex:SomeProtectionProfile .

ex:CCCertification rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ;
    rdf:type ex:CommonCriteriaCertification .

ex:SomeProtectionProfile rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ;
    rdf:type ex:ProtectionProfile .

# Axioms
ex:SomeCompositeSystem ex:hasComponent ex:SomeProduct .
```

We could also extend the OWL code with the SWRL rules [23], to enrich ontology functionality:

```
# SWRL Rules
[
    ex:Product(?p),
    ex:meetsProtectionProfile(?p, ?pp),
    ex:ProtectionProfile(?pp),
```

```
    swrlb:equal(?pp, ex:SomeProtectionProfile) ->
    ex:SomeProduct ex:achievesCertification ex:CCCertification
]
```

A two possible situation (use-cases) could be presented as:

```
# SWRL Rule 1
[
    # If a composite system has components and all
    # components achieve Common Criteria certification,
    # then the composite system achieves Common Criteria
    # certification.
    ex:CompositeSystem(?cs),
    ex:hasComponent(?cs, ?comp),
    ex:Product(?comp),
    ex:achievesCertification(?comp, ?cert),
    ex:CommonCriteriaCertification(?cert),
    swrlb:not(swrlb:equal(?comp, ?cs)) # Exclude the
    # composite system itself from the list of components
]
->
ex:achievesCertification(?cs, ?cert) # Inferred certification
# for the composite system

# SWRL Rule 2
[
    # If a product meets a specific protection profile,
    # then it achieves Common Criteria certification.
    ex:Product(?p),
    ex:meetsProtectionProfile(?p, ?pp),
    ex:ProtectionProfile(?pp),
    swrlb:equal(?pp, ex:SomeProtectionProfile)
]
->
ex:achievesCertification(?p, ex:CCCertification) # Inferred
# Common Criteria certification for the product
```

IV. EVALUATION AND VALIDATION

Evaluation and validation of the ontology may be very difficult and subjective because ontology development depend on the provided level of the domain knowledge. One domain can be presented on few different ways and formalized in different ontologies.

Anyway, for evaluation of the proposed ontology first method was to evaluate structure and this was done using the “Reasoner” and check with HermiT Reasoner [30] for any inconsistency. Ontology metrics can be seen in Figure 3 (no inconsistency or contradictions).

Second evaluation method was to check richness with class, relationship, attributes. The result can be seen in Figure 4.

It can be concluded that in this version there is no data properties and small numbers of individuals. Reason for this is that the ontology development is in early phase and user cases for the project are not yet defined.

```
INFO 07:49:33 ----- Running Reasoner -----
INFO 07:49:33 Pre-computing inferences:
INFO 07:49:33 - class hierarchy
INFO 07:49:33 - object property hierarchy
INFO 07:49:33 - data property hierarchy
INFO 07:49:33 - class assertions
INFO 07:49:33 - object property assertions
INFO 07:49:33 - same individuals
INFO 07:49:33 Ontologies processed in 83 ms by HermiT
INFO 07:49:33
```

Fig. 3. Checking ontology consistency with Reasoner

Ontology metrics	
Metrics	
Axiom	253
Logical axiom count	108
Declaration axioms count	87
Class count	65
Object property count	19
Data property count	0
Individual count	4
Annotation Property count	1

Fig. 4. Ontology metrics as a base for evaluation

It is expected that ontology will be enriched and changed with the next project phase when use-cases will be finished and fully defined.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed the development of an ontology specifically tailored for the cyber security certification of the composite systems. Furthermore, we introduced practical implications of the ontology in cyber security certification, and potential for automation and efficiency gains in this area.

As composite systems are comprised of multiple interconnected components, unique challenges for cyber security certification due to their dynamic nature and diverse elements and used technologies exists.

Introduced ontology is a structured framework for representing knowledge, allowing semantic interoperability and in future automated reasoning.

In addition, the practical implications of proposed ontology in streamlining certification procedures, enhancing risk management, and promoting trustworthiness in composite systems are emphasized.

In later research and development stages, new ontologies in cybersecurity related to certification of composite systems based on AI could be discussed and developed.

Through this paper, we contribute to the advancements of cyber security certification practices in EU and EU regulations in the context of evolving composite systems.

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